

Influence of Bank Innovative Strategies on Financial Performance of Listed Commercial Banks in Kenya

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾Damaseno Wechuli Khamala ⁽²⁾Dr Hesbon Otinga
Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, Kakamega, Kenya.

Abstract

Evidence from existing literature indicate conflicting relationships between banks innovativeness and banks' profitability, while other researches merely report on bank innovations without relating the effectiveness of the purported innovations on bank profitability. Therefore, lack of adequate empirical evidence on the relationship between emerging banks' innovativeness and bank profitability motivated this study to examine the influence of payment innovations, crowd funding, agency banking and artificial intelligence predictive banking system on profitability of listed commercial banks in Kenya. The study was guided by Innovation Diffusion theory. This research adopted explanatory survey research design. This study targeted managers from listed commercial banks headquarters in Nairobi city county, Kenya. The study sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's proportional sampling technique formula, which was drawn randomly from managers of commercial banks in Nairobi, Kenya. Primary data was collected by means of self-administered questionnaires. Data collected from the field was coded, cleaned, tabulated and analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics with the aid of specialized Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software and presented using tables to make them reader friendly. Descriptive statistics were used. Data was organized into graphs and tables for easy reference. Further, inferential statistics such as regression and correlation analyses was computed to determine both the nature and the strength of the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. Both descriptive and inferential statistics showed that the study's independent variable (agency banking) significantly influenced financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. The study concluded that commercial banks that effectively utilize agency banking system attract huge customer's base, save on transaction costs, thus boost bank's financial performance. The study recommends that one, commercial banks should roll out feasible agency banking products and services to win customer trust and boost their financial performance.

Keywords: *Innovative Strategies, Financial Performance*

Background of the study.

Turbulent financial performance of many financial lending institutions has attracted a myriad of researches on the most effective ways of mitigating financial loss, thus, the need for innovations. In this regard, Rosenbusch, Brinckmann and Bausch's (2011) meta-analysis of previous research on the relationship between innovation and firm performance aimed at establishing the direction and strength the relationship. Globally, in order to minimize costs, attract a larger market share and boost bank profitability in Brazil, private and state owned banks delivered financial services through retail agents including small supermarkets and pharmacies, post offices, and lottery kiosks. These agents are called banking correspondents (Kumar et al., 2006).

In January 2006, India's central bank issued a circular permitting banks to use post offices and specializes micro finance institutions, including nonprofit organizations cooperatives, and for profit companies as retail agents. The circular calls these agents business correspondents. In South Africa, branchless banking through retail agents is permitted only for licensed financial institutions (Harper *et al.*, 2016).

Chinese commercial banks' traditional businesses operations mode 'the wholesale credit operations' have been changing and the ratio of commercial banks' retail businesses have been increasing. The financial performances of commercial banks in Kenya have been in a generally turbulent financial trend and these have mainly been attributed to financial management issues and stiff competition from Micro finance institutions (CBK Annual

Report, 2018). statistics provide evidence of high concentration in the banking sector, which is likely to reduce small banks to mere followers and imitators of the financial innovations developed by large banks.

Statement of the Problem.

Banks innovativeness is meant to boost profitability but evidence from existing literature indicate conflicting relationships between banks innovativeness and banks' profitability, while other researches merely report on bank innovations without relating the effectiveness of the purported innovations on bank profitability(Cheng et al., 2017).

For instance, in Kenya, Central Bank of Kenya (2017) indicated that, the number of automated teller machines grew from 166 in 2001 to 2091 in 2010, debit cards increased from 160,000 in 2001 to over 6 million cards in subsequent years while mobile banking transactions increased from 48,000 per annum in 2007 to over 450,000 transactions per annum in 2017..

More so, some researchers have revealed conflicting results on the relationship between payment innovations and financial performance. For instance Gopalakrishnan (2013) study found a reverse causality between payment innovation and bank financial performance and recommended further researches. World Bank (2016) study reported that there was an opportunity for up to 344 million people in developing economies to participate in debt crowd funding, as a form of digital credit, but few banks are aware of the innovation.

Therefore, lack of adequate empirical evidence on the relationship between emerging banks' innovativeness and bank profitability motivated this study to examine the influence of agency banking on profitability of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

Objectives of the Study.

The general objective of the study was to examine influence of bank innovative systems on financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. The specific objective of this study include:-To evaluate influence of agency banking on financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

Research Hypothesis

H₀₁: Agency banking system does not significantly influence financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

Significance of the Study.

The study provided empirical data to investors / practitioners in the banking industry understand viable financial innovations that can minimize operational costs, attract and retain a large customer base and consequently boost bank profitability in terms of return on assets, return on investment and overall economic value. The study provided empirical evidence to financial researchers and scholars in understanding current trends in financial innovation in the banking industry, and their significant prediction on commercial banks profitability.

Scope of Study.

The study was only done on 12 listed commercial banks whose headquarters is in Nairobi County, and focused only on the influence of agency banking, payment innovations, crowd funding and artificial intelligence

predicting banking on financial performance of the 12 listed commercial banks. The study was done in June, 2020.

Limitation of Study.

The major challenge encountered was during data collection. First, most of the respondents were unwilling to participate in the study because they feared exposing information that could be de-marketing the institution. However, this limitation was overcome by assuring study participants that their confidentiality was maintained and that the study is purely for academic purposes. Further, as a measure of enhancing confidentiality, they were not supposed to write their names on the questionnaire

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical review

Innovation Diffusion theory

This theory proposed by Rogers (1983) asserts that factors which influence the diffusion of an innovation include; relative advantage (the extent to which a technology offers improvements over currently available tools), compatibility (its consistency with social practices and norms among its users), complexity (its ease of use or learning), trialability (the opportunity to try an innovation before committing to use it), and observability (the extent to which the technology's outputs and its gains are clear to see). These elements are not mutually exclusive thus unable to predict either the extent or the rate of innovation diffusion.

Further, while Rogers (1983) included image as an internal component of relative advantage, Moore and Benbasat (1991) found it to be an independent predictor of adoption. Image is the self-perception that adopting an innovation could result in enhanced social status. In this regard, the innovation diffusion theory describes the innovation-decision process within organizations, and is relevant to this study in that it helps in understanding how the characteristics of banking innovation interact to affect its adoption within the banking sector and its consequent on financial performance of commercial banks.

Independent Variables

Bank Innovative Systems

Dependent Variable

Commercial Banks Financial Performance

Review of study variables

Agency banking and bank financial performance

This evaluated the influence of adoption of agency banking mechanisms like customer/market segmenting, agent configurations, data/system security on profitability of commercial banks. For instance, Kumar et al, (2006), asserted that in a growing number of countries, banks and other commercial financial service providers are finding new ways to make money delivering financial services to unbanked people through agent banking system

That is rather than using bank branches and their own field officers, commercial banks offer banking and payment services through postal and retail outlets, including grocery stores, pharmacies, and gas stations among others. For low income people retail agents may be far more convenient and efficient than going through a bank. Banking through retail agents uses information and communication (Kumar et al, 2006).

Empirical review of literature related to the study

Agency banking and financial performance of banks

Chaia *et al.* (2011) study found that agent banking has become one of the most promising strategies for offering financial services in emerging markets. In this model, financial institutions work with networks of existing nonbank retail outlets such as convenience stores, gas stations, and post offices to deliver financial services. This approach can be especially powerful when serving the unbanked poor because of its ability to reduce banks costs and reach low income workers where they live. Agent banking benefits a range of stakeholders. The poor gain convenient access to financial services in their own communities. Financial institutions reach a vast new customer segment. Agents increase their sales volumes and have an opportunity to develop deeper relationships with the customer. However implementing correspondent strategies can be tough. It may be hard to build networks of partners that can fulfill the correspondent role.

Kumar *et al.* (2006) study initially found that Banking through retail agents is a concept that is beginning to appeal to policy makers and regulators. It has the potential to extend financial services to unbanked and marginalized communities. Agent – assisted banking is a relatively new concept. What makes agent banking work are information and communication technologies which customers, retail agents and banks use to record and communicate transaction details quickly, reliably and cheaply over vast distances. For example even in rural areas many poor people have access to low cost mobile phones and prepaid airtime dealers. For banks agent banking is used to reduce the cost of delivering financial services, relieve crowds in bank branches and establish presence in new areas.

Mas *et al.* (2018) study on commercial banks in South Africa, further found that agent banking systems receive a commission only if transactions are realized. On the other hand in a commercial bank branch, fixed costs are distributed over number of transactions resulting in significantly higher costs per transactions especially if the branch is under-utilized. As a result of lower transaction costs and a transaction driven revenue model, agent banking systems are more cost effective for transactional accounts with low balances and frequent transactions.

However on challenges to the profitability of agent banking by commercial banks, Mas *et al.* (2018) study reported that it is believed that banks cannot rely on agents to cross sell financial products. As a result, in order to increase overall customer profitability, banks may need to incur additional costs in marketing and deploying sales forces, including branch employees, to cross sell additional financial products to agent customers

Knowledge Gap

Evidence from the literature indicates that most of the studies on innovation and firm performance have been carried out in developed countries. However, critical success factors for innovation may not be replicable across geographical regions and markets due to cultural differences, but this cannot completely hinder their application

(Al-Ansari, Pervan & Xu 2013). Therefore lack of adequate empirical evidence on the significant role of emerging banking innovations in commercial banks motivated this study to examine the influence of agency banking on financial performance of listed Commercial banks.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research adopted explanatory survey research design. That is the explanatory survey research design is suitable for exploring relationships that are conducted in order to explain any behaviour or reactions of people to a given phenomenon in the society (Hair *et al.*, 2006). The explanatory survey design was therefore used to determine an association between the conceptualized independent and dependent variables as shown in the study's conceptual model.

Population of the Study.

This study targeted managers from 12 listed commercial banks headquarters in Nairobi city County, Kenya, stratified as shown in table 3.1; target population.

Table 3. 1: Target population

Category of employee	No. of targeted respondents
Internal audit managers	12
Risk Managers	12
Compliance Managers	12
ICT managers	12
Loans managers	12
Personal banking managers	12
Finance managers	12
Debt Collection Managers	12
Credit Managers	12
Human Resource Managers	12
Total	120

Sampling Frame

A sampling frame is a list of all the items in the population (Cooper & Schinder, (2007). That is, it is a complete list of everyone or everything you want to study or a list of things that you draw a sample from. In this study it consisted of senior managers of all listed commercial banks whose headquarters is in Nairobi city County, Kenya.

Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

Sample Size

In this study, the study sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's proportional sampling technique formula. The importance of this expression is that it gives a researcher the required sampling interval for a given population and a known sample. Therefore a sample size has been calculated as per Taro Yamane's proportional sampling technique formula shown as follows;

Sample

$$n = N / (1 + (e)^2)$$

Where n = Sample size

N = population under study

E = margin error (0.05)

I = constant

Therefore;

$$n = 120 / (1 + 120(0.05)^2)$$

$$n = 120 / (1 + 120(0.0025))$$

$$n = 120 / (1 + 0.3); n = 120 / 1.3$$

$$n = 92$$

From the calculation 92 and were drawn randomly from managers of commercial banks headquarters in Nairobi city county, Kenya as per the break down in table 3.2.

Table 3. 2: Sample Size

Category of Staff	No. of Senior Management Staff (N)	Sample n= (N/Target Pop.) x Sample size
Internal audit managers	12	10
Risk Managers	12	10
Compliance Managers	12	9
ICT managers	12	9
Loans managers	12	9
Personal banking managers	12	9
Finance managers	12	9
Debt Collection Mangers	12	9
Credit Managers	12	9
Human Resource Managers	12	9
Total	120	92

Sampling techniques

The study employed stratified random sampling technique which guided how sampled managers of commercial banks headquarters in Nairobi city county, Kenya, are to be selected. The stratified sampling technique ensured that it has minimized sample selection bias and ensures that certain elements of the population are not over represented or under represented.

Data collection Instruments

Primary data was collected by means of self-administered questionnaires. The questionnaires had structured questions. These questionnaires were structured and designed in multiple choice formats. Section one introduced the researcher, topic of research and its purpose to the respondent. Section two was designed to elicit demographic data of the respondents such as gender, level of education and age while section three dwelled on independent and dependent variable of the study.

Data collection procedure

As required by ethical practices in research, the researcher secured legitimate documents such as researcher's introductory letter, respondents' consent forms and a letter of identification from Jomo Kenya University of Science of Technology. The questionnaires were self-administered through sending hard copies of the questionnaires to the respondents and picking them when dully filled. In the process, the respondents were assured of confidentiality in that the information obtained was for the purpose of the study only.

Data Processing and analysis

Data collected from the field was coded, cleaned, tabulated and analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics with the aid of specialized Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).version 24 software. The output of analysis was presented using tables to make them reader friendly.

Descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages as well as measures of central tendency (means) and dispersion (standard deviation) was used. Data was also organized into graphs and tables for easy reference.

Further, inferential statistics such as regression and correlation analyses was used to determine both the nature and the strength of the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. Correlation analysis is usually used together with regression analysis to measure how well the regression line explains the variation of the dependent variable. The linear and multiple regression plus correlation analyses were based on the association between two (or more) variables. SPSS version 24 is the analysis computer software that was used to compute statistical data.

Study conceptualized Regression Model;

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + e$$

y = financial performance of commercial banks in Nairobi city County

β_0 = Constant

X_1 = agency banking

{ β_0 - β_4 } = Beta coefficients

e = the error term

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.2 Response Rate.

From 92 questionnaires that were dispatched for data collection, 77 questionnaires were returned completely filled, representing a response rate of 83.6% which is good for generalizability of the research findings to a wider population. The high response rate was achieved because the researcher patiently waited for respondents to completely fill the questionnaire before picking them.

Reliability and Validity of Research Instruments

Validity of research instruments was checked using content validity where all questions were checked for clarity of words and ensuring all questions had adequate content as per the study variables. Reliability of research instruments was tested using Cronbach alpha; which tests internal consistency and the results in table 4.1 shows Cronbach alpha coefficients values of 0.7 and above confirming that reliability of the study's research instruments.

Table 4. 1: Results of Reliability test

Variable	Number of items	Cronbach alpha
Agency banking	6	.811
Financial performance	6	.815

Descriptive statistics: Agency banking and banks' financial performance

These are summarized responses on whether agency banking innovation influence financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. The descriptive results are presented in table 4.3.

Table 4. 2: Descriptive statistics; Agency banking system

Statement	5	4	3	2	1	Mean	Std. Dev
1.The agent bankers are well trained in agent banking	16(20.8)	34(44.2)	8(10.4)	12(15.5)	7(9.1)	3.52	0.924
2.Agency banking is well configured to conveniently match the bank standard operating procedures	10(13.0)	27(35.1)	17(22.1)	12(15.6)	11(14.2)	3.37	0.926
3.Most bank's customers are attracted to the agency banking system	13(16.9)	37(48.1)	8(10.4)	10(13)	9(11.6)	3.49	0.925
4.The agency banking platform has catered for all market or customer segments	9(11.7)	39(50.6)	9(11.7)	8(10.4)	12(15.6)	3.32	0.927
5.Customer data is well captured and secured by the agency22 banking system	11(14.3)	33(42.9)	12(15.6)	10(13)	11(14.2)	3.39	0.928
6.Generally, the bank has realized a significant growth in its financial performance after adoption of the agency banking systems	13(16.9)	38(49.3)	9(11.7)	9(11.7)	8(10.4)	3.51	0.929
Valid list wise=77							
Grand mean =3.43							

From table 4.3, most respondents agreed (44.2%) that the agent bankers are well trained in agent banking while 15.5% disagreed to the statement, implying that there are banks who have not well trained their agents which could hamper the effectiveness of the agency banking innovation. More closely, only 35.1% agreed while 22.1% of respondents were uncertain that agency banking is well configured to conveniently match the bank standard operating procedures; thus revealing existence of inefficiency of some of agency banking operations experienced by customers.

Further, while 48.1% of respondents agreed that most bank's customers are attracted to the agency banking system, 13.0% disagreed revealing existence of techno phobia by some customers who fear the riskiness associated with agent banking. More so 50.6% of respondents agreed that the agency banking platform has catered for all market or customer segments, while 42.9% of respondents also agreed that customer data is well captured and secured by the agency banking system; thus indicating that agency banking has not really been embraced by some bank customers.

Lastly, most respondents agreed (49.3%) and strongly agreed (16.9%) that generally, the bank has realized a significant growth in its financial performance after adoption of the agency banking systems; implying that cost savings brought about by agency banking innovation boosts bank's financial performance. This is supported by Kumar et al. (2006), assertion that in a growing number of countries, banks and other commercial financial service providers are finding new ways to make money delivering financial services to unbanked people through agent banking system, thus boosts bank's financial performance.

Inferential Statistics

Assumptions of multiple regression analysis

First, test of linearity refers to the degree to which the change in the dependent variable is related to the change in the independent variable. This was tested by correlation coefficients and correlation results showed that independent variable (agency banking) has significant correlation with the dependent variable (financial performance) as shown in table 4.7 on correlation analysis.

Table 4. 3: Correlations

		Agency Banking	Payment innovations	Crowd funding	AI predictive banking	Financial performance
Agency Banking	Pearson Correlation	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)					
	N	77				
Financial performance	Pearson Correlation	.825**	.753**	.676**	.718**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	77	77	77	77	77

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Secondly, multicollinearity tests whether two or more conceptualized independent variables are highly correlated with each other. This leads to problems with understanding which independent variable contributes to the variance explained in the dependent variable, as well as statistical problems in calculating a multiple regression model. This assumption was tested using correlation analysis. Most researchers insist that if correlation coefficient, (r) is close to 1 or -1, then there is multicollinearity but if correlation coefficient (r) is not above 0.9, then there is no multicollinearity In this study (table 4.6 on correlation analysis), the highest correlation coefficient between all pairs of independent variables (agency banking, payment innovations, crowd funding, artificial intelligence predictive banking) is 0.825, which is below the threshold of 0.9, thus multicollinearity assumption was checked and met.

Thirdly, normality test assumption asserts that data must have a normal distribution and this was tested by the use histograms with normal curve. The results (in the appendix) show histograms with bell-shaped normal curves indicating that data was approximately normally distributed, thus met this assumption.

Lastly, as a statistical rule, since the researcher collected categorical data on independent and dependent variables, the collected categorical data was first summated and transformed into continuous data using SPSS to allow running of correlations, linear and multiple regressions analyses.

Linear regression results

This tested the linear influence of agency banking on financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. This was computed by SPSS based on transformed data from categorical data to continuous data so as to run regression analyses based on continuous data.

Linear influence of agency banking on financial performance

This tested the direct influence of agency banking on financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. The results are shown table 4.8.

Table 4. 4: Direct influence of agency banking on financial performance

Model Summary										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			Sig. F Change	
						F Change	df1	df2		
1	.825 ^a	.680	.676	.69397	.680	159.562	1	75	.000	
ANOVA ^b										
Model	Sum of Squares		Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.				
1	Regression		76.844	1	76.844	159.562			.000 ^a	
	Residual		36.120	75	.482					
	Total		112.964	76						
Coefficients ^a										
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			T	Sig.		
		B	Std. Error	Beta						
1	(Constant)	.682	.232			2.945			.004	
	Agency Banking	.919	.073			.825	12.632			.000

a. Dependent Variable: Financial performance

From table 4.8, the model summary shows that $R^2 = 0.680$; implying that 68.0% variations in the financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya is explained by agency banking while other factors not in the study model accounts for 32.0% of variation in financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. Further, coefficient analysis shows that agency banking has positive significant influence on financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya ($\beta = 0.919$ (0.073); *at* $p < .01$). This implies that a single improvement in effective agency banking innovations will lead to 0.919 unit increase in the financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. Therefore, the linear regression equation is;

$$(i) y = 0.682 + 0.919X_1$$

Where;

y = financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

X_1 = agency banking innovation.

Multiple regression analysis

Multiple regression analysis was computed to assess the multivariate influence of the study's independent variables (agency banking) on the dependent variable (financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya). This was after the compulsory assumptions of multiple regression analyses were checked and met. The multiple regression results are shown in table 4.12.

Table 4. 5: Multiple regression results

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			Sig. F Change
						F Change	df1	df2	
1	.851 ^a	.724	.708	.65825	.724	47.177	4	72	.000
ANOVA ^b									
Model	Sum of Squares		Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.			
1	Regression		81.767	4	20.442	47.177			.000 ^a
	Residual		31.197	72	.433				
	Total		112.964	76					

a. Predictors: (Constant), Agency Banking.

b. Dependent Variable: Financial performance

Multiple regression analysis in table 4.12 shows the multiple regression results of the combined influence of the study's independent variable (agency banking). The model's R squared (R^2) is 0.724 which shows that the study explains 72.4% of variation in the financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya, while other factors not in the conceptualized study model accounts for 27.6 %, hence, it is a good study model.

Furthermore, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) shows the mean squares and F statistics significant ($F = 47.177$; significant at $p < .001$), thus confirming the fitness of the model and also implies that the study's independent variable (agency banking) has significant variations in their contributions to financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

Finally, the values of unstandardized regression coefficients with standard errors in parenthesis in table 4.13 indicate that all the study's independent variable (agency banking; $\beta = 0.613$ (0.151) at $p < 0.05$ significantly influenced financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya (dependent variable).

In this regard, the study's final multiple regression equation is;

$$(v) y = 0.610 + 0.613X_1$$

Where;

y= financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya

X_1 = agency banking

Table 4. 6: Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.610	.151		4.035	.000
Agency Banking	.613	.151	.550	4.070	.000
AI predictive banking	.426	.138	.400	3.080	.003

a. Dependent Variable: Financial performance

Testing of study hypotheses

First, **study hypothesis one (H_{01})** stated that agency banking system does not significantly influence financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. Multiple regression results indicate that agency banking significantly influence financial performance of listed commercial banks ($\beta = 0.568$ (0.079) at $p < 0.05$).

Hypothesis one is therefore rejected. The results indicate that that a single improvement in effective agency banking innovations will lead to 0.613 unit increase in the financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya.

The results are supported by Mas et.al. (2018) study on commercial banks in South Africa, further found that agent banking systems receive a commission only if transactions are realized. On the other hand in a commercial bank branch, fixed costs are distributed over number of transactions resulting in significantly higher costs per transactions especially if the branch is under-utilized. As a result of lower transaction costs and a transaction driven revenue model, agent banking systems are more cost effective for transactional accounts with low balances and frequent transactions.

Chaia et al. (2011) study found that agent banking has become one of the most promising strategies for offering financial services in emerging markets. In this model, financial institutions work with networks of existing nonbank retail outlets such as convenience stores, gas stations, and post offices to deliver financial services. This approach can be especially powerful when serving the unbanked poor because of its ability to reduce banks costs and reach low income workers where they live. Agent banking benefits a range of stakeholders. The poor gain convenient access to financial services in their own communities, financial institutions reach a vast new

customer segment. Agents increase their sales volumes and have an opportunity to develop deeper relationships with the customer which then enhances bank's financial performance.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Summary of the Study.

The general objective of the study is to examine influence of bank innovative systems on financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. The study tested research hypothesis H_{01} : Agency banking system does not significantly influence financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya; This tested the influence of agency banking system on financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. The study found that agency banking systems like customer/market segmenting, agent configurations, data/system security affect financial performance of banks.

The study results are consisted with earlier researchers that found that agent banking benefits a range of stakeholders; for instance, the poor gain convenient access to financial services in their own communities, financial institutions reach a vast new customer segment. That is agents increase their sales volumes and have an opportunity to develop deeper relationships with the customer which then enhances bank's financial performance.

Conclusion.

Based on the above findings, the study concludes that commercial banks that effectively utilize agency banking system attract huge customer's base, save on transaction costs, thus boost bank's financial performance.

Recommendation

The study recommends that commercial banks should roll out feasible agency banking products and services to would be customers located in areas where manual-over the counter banking services cannot be accessed.

Areas for Further Study

First, a similar study can be done on all commercial banks in Kenya using time series analysis so as to compare study findings. Secondly, a similar study can be done on Micro Finance Banking institutions so as to assess the effectiveness of the adopted banking innovations.

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